

ARCHEOSTORIE®
JOURNAL *of* PUBLIC
ARCHAEOLOGY

VOLUME 3 / 2019

Topic of the Year: Museum Archaeology

ARCHEOSTORIE™
JOURNAL *of* PUBLIC
ARCHAEOLOGY

VOLUME 3 / 2019

www.archeostoriejpa.eu

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Alessandra Cilio

Excellence and craft. A network of museums to challenge post-earthquake crisis in the Marche

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Abstract

The Research Project 'Techne' (Ancient TECHnologies and workshop NETwork) aims at reconstructing and investigating the origins, the historical development and cultural context, the technical aspects of craftsmanship, and at retrieving the excellence of artisan activities in the Marche as a contribution to re-challenge the territory after the seism. The purpose is to constitute a network of museums dedicated to craftsmanship, starting from a pilot experience (Museo della Tela, Macerata), in which past and present meet. Through a diachronic and multidisciplinary approach, the project involves different stakeholders, i.e. the University, the local administrations, private societies and inland communities, those majorly suffering the consequences of the earthquake.

Open Access Peer Reviewed Keywords: the Marche, earthquake, craftsmanship, museum, excellence

Between August 2016 and January 2017 – although the very last, rather strong, shake of the seismic swarm was registered on September 1st 2019 – a large area along the ridge of the Central Appennines, encompassing the regions of the Marche, Umbria, Lazio and Abruzzo, was struck by three major earthquakes of a magnitude of 6.0 or higher (6.5 that occurring on October 30th 2016). This catastrophe caused 301 casualties, more than 388 injuries, the demise of several hamlets, and a series of devastations, still adversely affecting the life of those who managed to survive.

The seismic crater (Figure 1) occupying an area of circa 8,000 sq. km includes 140 municipalities – 87 only in the Marche –, distributed in ten different provinces between the Alta Valle del Tronto, the Sibillines, the Laga Mountains, and the Alto Aterno Mounts (Decreto-Legge 17 ottobre 2016, n. 189, allegato 1, allegato 2, allegato 2bis).

The assistance of those seeking shelter was indeed a major priority, but the safeguard of the artistic patrimony was among the first actions undertaken by state authorities to guarantee also the memory of a shared past (of traditions) and the future local economy, much tied to tourism.

To tackle the emergency one of the measures

taken by national and local authorities was to move people towards secure sites of the coast in expectation of signs of a return to normality, wishing and striving for a rapid reconstruction even of the small inland villages, as Arquata del Tronto, completely abandoned after the second seismic wave in October 2016.

The resettlement along the Adriatic coast – meant to be temporary – implied banally not only the abandonment of their houses and burghs, but also the asset freeze of all the economic activities. As a consequence, besides the evident dramatic loss of houses and properties, most of the earthquake victims had to close medium and small family-run businesses, namely agro-food activities and craft workshops, constituting the large basis of the productive system of these regions. As a result, this engendered the loss of many jobs.

These evident difficulties have been undermining the effective and prompt economical and psychological restart and, in general, the delay of the recovery process.

A secondary effect of this (progressive) crisis of the local economy, based on family-run businesses, is the silent loss of the rich patrimony of artisanal knowledge, often transmitted from father to son, which constitutes the foundation